

Best Linear Unbiased Estimators Based on Order Statistics with An Application to Environmental Data

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Abstract

Environmental data provides insights into how environmental factors, such as pollution and climate conditions, affect human health. This information is crucial for developing policies to protect public health. Environmental data can include extreme values or outliers due to unusual events, such as a sudden spike in pollution or an unusually high temperature. These outliers can distort the normality of the data. Recently, Sanaullah et al. (2019) and Ahmad et al. (2023) introduced new ratio-type estimators based on the BLUE estimator proposed by Lloyd in 1952. Our study assesses the robustness of Lloyd's location estimator and compares it with other well-established robust estimators, such as Huber's M, Tiku's modified maximum likelihood and Tukey's estimator through a comprehensive simulation study. Overall, BLUE-type balances robustness and efficiency in small datasets, MMLE excels under uncontaminated long tail symmetric (LTS) data, and Huber maintains general robustness across larger samples. We also illustrate the performance of these estimators using a real-life example from environmental data.

Key Words: BLUE, Modified Maximum Likelihood, Order Statistics, Location-scale families, Robustness.

1. Introduction

In survey sampling theory, when auxiliary information on a variable z is available that is correlated with the study variable y , it is often used to develop improved estimators of the population mean \bar{Y} . The classical ratio estimator is one of the most widely used examples of such estimators (Cochran 1940). When the study variable y is highly positively correlated with the auxiliary variable z , the classical ratio estimator performs better than the simple mean-per-unit estimator, leading to more precise estimates of the population mean (Prasad 1989, Sani 2023). The conventional ratio estimator is defined as:

$$\bar{y}_1 = \left(\frac{\bar{y}}{\bar{z}}\right)\bar{Z},$$

where \bar{y} and \bar{z} denote the sample means of the study and auxiliary variables, respectively, and \bar{Z} is the known population mean of the auxiliary variable. This estimator performs optimally when both y and z follow a normal distribution and are linearly related (Murthy 1967, Swain 2014). However, in practice, the assumption of normality is often violated. Data may contain outliers, skewness, or heavy tails. Under such non-normal conditions, the performance of the classical ratio estimator often poor. Recent studies have focused on improving robustness under non-normality and contamination. In robust statistics, a novel method of estimation for location and scale parameters using Modified Maximum Likelihood (MML) was developed (Tiku and Suresh 1992). This approach replaced the classical likelihood equations with modified forms that remain valid and efficient even under heavy-tailed or censored data. Building upon Tiku's work, studies applied the MML method to the ratio estimation framework under data anomalies (Oral and Kadilar 2011). Others proposed BLUE-type estimators that replace the sample mean with a location parameter estimated via Best Linear Unbiased Estimation based on order statistics (Ahmad, Sanaullah et al. 2020). The general form of the proposed ratio estimator is:

$$\bar{y}_2 = \left(\frac{\hat{\mu}_y^*}{\bar{z}}\right)\bar{Z},$$

where $\hat{\mu}_y^*$ represents the BLUE-type estimator of the location parameter. These studies showed that using order statistics in place of raw sample means enhances robustness and efficiency under mild deviations from normality. They examined the properties of their proposed ratio estimator within the survey-sampling framework.

Despite these considerable contributions, the robustness characteristics of the BLUE-type estimator itself, particularly its performance under long-tailed symmetric distributions, mixture contamination, and small-sample conditions, have not been comprehensively studied. A systematic evaluation of these properties is essential to assess the estimator's practical utility in modern applications, such as environmental and biomedical data analysis, where heavy tails and outliers are common. Our primary objective was to evaluate the robustness properties of the BLUE-type location estimator under various data conditions, including long-tailed symmetric distributions and contamination scenarios. We compared the BLUE-type estimators with other established robust estimators, such as Tiku's Modified Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MMLE) and Huber's M-estimator, to assess their relative performance in terms of bias, variance, and efficiency. Additionally, we aimed to demonstrate the practical performance of these estimators through an application to environmental temperature data, a context where non-normality and outliers are frequently encountered. This illustrates how BLUE-type estimators can provide stable and reliable parameter estimates in datasets affected by extreme observations.

1.1 Long-Tailed Symmetric (LTS) Distribution

In many real-world applications, the underlying distributions of the observed variables deviate from normality and often exhibit heavy tails or outliers. The Long-Tailed Symmetric (LTS) distribution family provides a flexible framework for modeling such data. It generalizes the normal distribution by introducing a shape parameter that controls the tail behavior while preserving symmetry about a central location.

Let X denote a random variable following the LTS family, characterized by the parameters μ (location), σ (scale), and p (shape). The probability density function (pdf) can be expressed as:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma k^{1/2} \beta\left(\frac{1}{2}, p - \frac{1}{2}\right)} \left\{ 1 + \frac{(x - \mu)^2}{k\sigma^2} \right\}^{-p}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty$$

where, $k = 2p-3$ and $p \geq 2$. LTS family especially useful is its adaptive nature with respect to the value of p . When p is small, the distribution exhibits heavier tails, allowing it to accommodate extreme values or outliers more effectively. As p increases, the distribution becomes increasingly concentrated around the mean, and in the limit as $p \rightarrow \infty$, it converges to the normal distribution. As p decreases, the tails become progressively heavier, resembling the *Student's t* or *Laplace* distributions. The LTS family therefore encompasses a broad range of symmetric distributions commonly used for robust modeling of data contaminated by extreme observations. By varying the shape parameter p , we can systematically control the degree of tail heaviness and evaluate the robustness and efficiency of competing estimators. In this study, our interest is in the location parameter μ .

1.2 Modified Maximum Likelihood (MML) Estimator

The Modified Maximum Likelihood (MML) method, originally introduced by Tiku and Suresh (1992), provides an effective alternative to the classical maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) technique, particularly when data deviate from normality or contain outliers. The key idea behind the MML method is to replace the nonlinear components of the likelihood equations with linearized approximations based on expected values of order statistics. Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n be a random sample of size n from LTS; p is assumed known. The likelihood function is:

$$L(x, \mu, \sigma) \propto \left(\frac{1}{\sigma}\right)^n \prod \left(1 + \frac{(x_i - \mu)^2}{\kappa\sigma^2}\right)^{-p}$$

To obtain the maximum likelihood equations, we differentiate the log-likelihood with respect to μ and σ , and equate the results to zero:

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \mu} = \frac{2p}{\kappa\sigma} \sum g(z_i) = 0$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \ln L}{\partial \sigma} = -\frac{n}{\sigma} + \frac{2p}{\kappa \sigma} \sum z_i g(z_i) = 0$$

where, $g(z_i) = \frac{z_i}{1 + \frac{1}{\kappa} z_i^2}$ and $z_i = \frac{(x_i - \mu)}{\sigma}$.

However, these equations are nonlinear in μ and σ and therefore do not yield explicit analytical solutions. So, we re-write the equations using order statistics which are the sorted values of the sample and then apply a Taylor series expansion to linearize the nonlinear parts to solve it. By solving these equations we get, the location estimator as:

$$\hat{\mu} = \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i x_{(i)}}{m} \right\} \quad \text{where} \quad m = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i$$

And the scale estimator as:

$$\hat{\sigma} = \left\{ \frac{B + \sqrt{B^2 + 4nC}}{2\sqrt{n(n-1)}} \right\}$$

Where, $B = \frac{2p}{k} \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i x_{(i)}$ and $C = \frac{2p}{k} \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \{x_{(i)} - \hat{\mu}\}^2 = \frac{2p}{k} \{\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i x_{(i)}^2 - m\hat{\mu}^2\}$.

These estimates are computationally efficient and robust, especially in the presence of outliers or heavy tails.

1.3 M-Estimator (Huber, 1981)

The Huber's M-estimator remains one of the most widely used methods in robust statistics, particularly for estimating location and scale parameters in the presence of outliers. The fundamental idea behind M-estimators is to minimize a loss function that penalizes deviations from the center of the data distribution (Huber 1984). The Huber M-estimator for the location parameter μ is defined as:

$$\hat{\mu} = \arg \min_{\mu} \sum_{i=1}^n L_{\delta}(x_i - \mu)$$

And the Huber M-estimator for the scale parameter σ is obtained by minimizing the Huber loss applied to standardized residuals such as:

$$\hat{\sigma} = \arg \min_{\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^n L_{\delta} \left(\frac{x_i - \hat{\mu}}{\sigma} \right)$$

Here, $r_i = x_i - \mu$ represents the residuals with Huber loss function defined as:

$$L_{\delta}(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} r^2 & \text{for } |r| \leq \delta \\ \delta \left(|r| - \frac{1}{2} \delta \right) & \text{for } |r| > \delta \end{cases}$$

Huber also defined a corresponding weight function, which determines how much each data point contributes to the estimation process based on its residual. Points close to the center of the data receive full weight (behaving like least squares). Whereas points farther away (outliers) are down-weighted, contributing less to the final estimate. The weight function is defined as:

$$w(r_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |r_i| \leq \delta, \\ \frac{\delta}{|r_i|} & \text{if } |r_i| > \delta \end{cases}$$

1.4 Best Linear Unbiased (BLUE)-Type Estimator (Lloyd, 1952)

The Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE), or BLUE-type estimator is an efficient and theoretically sound approach to estimating parameters when the data are modeled as a linear function of order statistics (Lloyd 1952). Let $y_{(1)} \leq y_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq y_{(n)}$ be the order statistics of a random sample of size n from a location-scale distribution:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma} f \left(\frac{y - \mu}{\sigma} \right)$$

The BLUE-type estimator can be formulated within a linear regression framework as:

$$y = w\theta + \varepsilon$$

where, y is the vector of ordered sample observations i.e. the order statistics, $\theta = [\mu, \sigma]^T$, the vector of unknown parameters, location and scale, w is the $n \times 2$ design matrix, where t_i are expected standardized order statistics and $\varepsilon = [\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \dots, \varepsilon_n]^T$, the vector of random errors with $E(\varepsilon) = 0$ and $\text{Var}(\varepsilon) = \Omega$. To find the BLUE-type estimator we differentiate the following equation:

$$\varepsilon' \Omega^{-1} \varepsilon = (y - w\theta)' \Omega^{-1} (y - w\theta)$$

Here, V denotes the variance-covariance matrix of the order statistics, which captures the correlation structure among the ordered sample values. Finding the variance-covariance matrix for order statistics is challenging. For small sample sizes, we used the exact variances and covariances tabulated by (Tiku and Kumra 1985). These tabulations provide reliable reference values for symmetric distributions, allowing precise computation of the BLUE-type weights w_i . However, for larger sample sizes ($n > 20$), obtaining exact tabulated values becomes computationally intensive. Therefore, we used the approximations proposed by (Arnold and Balakrishnan 2012). Let,

$$p_i = \frac{i}{n+1}$$

$$q_i = 1 - \frac{i}{n+1}$$

$$p_j = \frac{j}{n+1}$$

$$q_j = 1 - \frac{j}{n+1} \quad (i=1, 2, \dots, n)$$

Then, for $i \leq j$, the covariance between the i^{th} and j^{th} order statistics, denoted as $\text{Cov}(X_{(i)}, X_{(j)})$, is approximated by:

$$\text{Cov}(X_{(i)}, X_{(j)}) = \frac{\pi_i \cdot q_j}{n+2} \cdot dG_i \cdot dG_j + \frac{\pi_i \cdot q_j}{(n+2)^2} \left[(q_i - \pi_i) \cdot ddG_i \cdot dG_j + (q_j - p_j) \cdot ddG_j \cdot dG_i + 0.5 \cdot \pi_i \cdot q_i \cdot dddG_i \cdot dG_j + 0.5 \cdot p_j \cdot q_j \cdot dddG_j \cdot dG_i + 0.5 \cdot \pi_i \cdot q_j \cdot ddG_i \cdot ddG_j \right]$$

where $G(\cdot)$ denotes the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the parent distribution, and dG_i , d^2G_i , d^3G_i represent the first, second, and third derivatives of G evaluated at the quantiles corresponding to p_i . The resulting $n \times n$ matrix $\Omega = [\text{Cov}(X_{(i)}, X_{(j)})]$ is then used in the computation of the BLUE-type estimator:

$$\hat{\theta} = (w^T \Omega^{-1} w)^{-1} w^T \Omega^{-1} y.$$

The estimator for the location parameter μ is then expressed as a linear combination of order statistics:

$$\hat{\mu}_{BLUE} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_{(i)},$$

where the weights w_i are derived from the covariance matrix Ω such that $\sum w_i = 1$.

2. Simulation Study

To evaluate the robustness properties of the Best Linear Unbiased (BLUE)-type estimator, we conducted an extensive Monte Carlo simulation study comparing its performance with two established robust estimators: Tiku's Modified Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MMLE) and the Huber M-estimator. The primary goal was to assess the relative efficiency, bias, and variance of these estimators under a range of contamination and distributional settings, reflecting realistic data conditions often encountered in practice. We considered four different cases in our simulations, each representing a distinct data-generating mechanism:

1. True Model (LTS with $\mu=0$, $\sigma=1$, $p=2.5$)
2. Outlier Model (no. of outliers, $r = [0.1n + 0.5]$ where outliers $\sim t(0, c^2)$ with $df=2p-1$)
3. Mixture Model (0.90LTS + 0.10 Laplace)

4. Contaminated Model (0.90LTS ($\mu=0, \sigma=1$) + 0.10 LTS ($\mu=0, \sigma=c$))

We considered several sample sizes $n = 10, 15, 500$ to explore both small-sample and large-sample behavior, and contamination levels characterized by $c = 2, 3, 4$. Each simulation scenario was replicated 5,000 times to ensure stable estimates. For each estimator and simulation case, we computed the bias and variance of the estimated location parameter. To quantify and compare performance, we calculated the Relative Efficiency (RE) of the MMLE and Huber estimators with respect to the BLUE-type estimator, defined as:

$$RE = \frac{MSE_{mml}}{MSE_{BLUE}} \text{ or } RE = \frac{MSE_{huber}}{MSE_{BLUE}}$$

where MSE denotes the mean squared error of the corresponding estimator. An RE value greater than 1 indicates that the BLUE-type estimator is more efficient, while a value less than 1 indicates higher efficiency of MMLE or Huber relative to BLUE-type.

2.1 Simulation Results

Based on simulation results, BLUE-type estimators are more robust for estimating the location parameter in small samples when using LTS. This advantage may not hold for other distributions. They also show higher efficiency than MMLE and Huber estimators in small samples, as they assign lower weights to tail observations, effectively reducing the influence of extremes.

2.1.1 True model (No assumption violations)

When data were generated from LTS without outliers (Table 1), all three estimators produced nearly unbiased location estimates across sample sizes. MMLE had slightly smaller standard errors than BLUE-type and Huber, indicating marginally higher efficiency, while Huber showed the lowest standard deviation for small samples. BLUE-type estimators were robust in small samples, giving less weight to extreme values and maintaining accuracy.

Table 1: Results when data is from LTS

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	0.00000	-0.00257	0.00053
mu_mml	0.00029	-0.00261	0.00031
mu_huber	0.00012	-0.00201	0.00033
sd_blue	1.23592	1.15804	1.06642
sd_mle	1.11575	1.07628	1.01092
sd_huber	0.73934	0.75552	0.77539
Bias_mu_blue	0.00000	-0.00257	0.00053
Bias_mu_mml	0.00029	-0.00261	0.00031
Bias_mu_huber	0.00012	-0.00201	0.00033
Bias_sd_blue	0.23592	0.15804	0.00642
Bias_sd_mle	0.11575	0.07628	0.01092
Bias_sd_huber	-0.26066	-0.24448	-0.22461
MSE_mu_blue	0.07311	0.04942	0.00176
MSE_mu_mml	0.07420	0.04937	0.00141
MSE_mu_huber	0.07435	0.05068	0.00143
MSE_sd_blue	0.21616	-0.11208	0.00246
MSE_sd_mml	0.16437	0.08740	0.00205
MSE_sd_huber	0.15428	0.12367	0.05227
RE_mu_mml_vs_blue	1.01481	0.99912	0.79757
RE_sd_mml_vs_blue	0.76042	0.77979	0.83015
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	1.01692	1.02555	0.81171

2.1.2 Outlier model

Introducing 2–4 outliers (Tables 2–4) increased bias and MSE for all methods, particularly for BLUE-type and MMLE. Huber estimators remained robust, showing smaller MSE for both location and scale parameters, especially in small samples. BLUE-type maintained reasonable efficiency but showed larger scale bias as the number of outliers increased. These results confirm that Huber effectively downweights extreme observations in contaminated data, whereas BLUE-type is more sensitive to multiple outliers.

Table 2: Results when data is from LTS when 2 outliers

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	0.00267	0.00096	0.00088
mu_mml	0.00296	0.00145	0.00069
mu_huber	0.00276	0.00061	0.00065
sd_blue	1.48348	1.29399	1.11800
sd_mle	1.35457	1.21867	1.11482
sd_huber	0.84390	0.81511	0.82323
Bias_mu_blue	0.00267	0.00096	0.00088
Bias_mu_mml	0.00296	0.00145	0.00069
Bias_mu_huber	0.00276	0.00061	0.00065
Bias_sd_blue	0.48348	0.29399	0.11800
Bias_sd_mle	0.35457	0.21867	0.11482
Bias_sd_huber	-0.15610	-0.18489	-0.17677
MSE_mu_blue	0.10185	0.06095	0.00235
MSE_mu_mml	0.10576	0.06147	0.00166
MSE_mu_huber	0.10326	0.06259	0.00169
MSE_sd_blue	0.49963	0.20219	0.01743
MSE_sd_mml	0.39494	0.16666	0.01575
MSE_sd_huber	0.13762	0.10834	0.03337
RE_mu_mml_vs_blue	1.04152	1.00847	0.70472
RE_sd_mml_vs_blue	0.79046	0.82428	0.90384
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	1.01675	1.02693	0.72019
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.27545	0.53582	1.91498

Table 3: Results when data is from LTS when 3 outliers

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	0.00091	-0.00392	-0.00079
mu_mml	0.00003	-0.00368	-0.00067
mu_huber	-0.00019	-0.00427	-0.00080
sd_blue	1.73389	1.42432	1.23620
sd_mle	1.62395	1.37281	1.21738
sd_huber	0.89480	0.84920	0.84392
Bias_mu_blue	0.00091	-0.00392	-0.00079
Bias_mu_mml	0.00003	-0.00368	-0.00067
Bias_mu_huber	-0.00019	-0.00427	-0.00080
Bias_sd_blue	0.73389	0.42432	0.23620
Bias_sd_mle	0.62395	0.37281	0.21738
Bias_sd_huber	-0.10520	-0.15080	-0.15608
MSE_mu_blue	0.11845	0.06508	0.00341
MSE_mu_mml	0.12674	0.06634	0.00178
MSE_mu_huber	0.11809	0.06772	0.00179
MSE_sd_blue	0.97637	0.34192	0.06137
MSE_sd_mml	0.94380	0.33064	0.05110
MSE_sd_huber	0.14157	0.10695	0.02660
RE_mu_mml_vs_blue	1.07001	1.01935	0.52176

RE_sd_mmle_vs_blue	0.96665	0.96699	0.83269
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	0.99699	1.04052	0.52594
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.14499	0.31280	0.43349

Table 3: Results when data is from LTS when 4 outliers

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	-0.00132	-0.00575	0.00149
mu_mmle	-0.00126	-0.00596	0.00069
mu_huber	-0.00146	-0.00490	0.00061
sd_blue	1.99776	1.64840	1.35953
sd_mle	1.92455	1.53291	1.32276
sd_huber	0.92836	0.87036	0.86542
Bias_mu_blue	-0.00132	-0.00575	0.00149
Bias_mu_mmle	-0.00126	-0.00596	0.00069
Bias_mu_huber	-0.00146	-0.00490	0.00061
Bias_sd_blue	0.99776	0.64840	0.35953
Bias_sd_mle	0.92455	0.53291	0.32276
Bias_sd_huber	-0.07168	-0.12964	-0.14468
MSE_mu_blue	0.15209	0.06996	0.00470
MSE_mu_mmle	0.16989	0.07237	0.00191
MSE_mu_huber	0.14603	0.07197	0.00193
MSE_sd_blue	1.66026	0.49150	0.13750
MSE_sd_mmle	1.75287	0.53714	0.10944
MSE_sd_huber	0.14850	0.10299	0.02319
RE_mu_mmle_vs_blue	1.11701	1.04039	0.41070
RE_sd_mmle_vs_blue	1.05578	1.09285	0.79594
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	0.96013	1.03465	0.40729
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.08945	0.20954	0.16862

2.1.3 Mixed Models

For mixtures of LTS with Laplace contamination (Tables 5–7), MMLE and BLUE-type estimators experienced moderate increases in bias and MSE, particularly for scale. Huber remained robust, maintaining low MSE even under moderate contamination, though efficiency for location decreased slightly in small samples.

Table 5: Results when data is from 0.90LTS + 0.10Laplace (0,c=2)

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	0.00332	0.00563	-0.00070
mu_mmle	0.00326	0.00648	-0.00019
mu_huber	0.00419	0.00637	-0.00024
sd_blue	1.35421	1.25923	1.11630
sd_mle	1.23129	1.18125	1.11316
sd_huber	0.78664	0.80283	0.82292
Bias_mu_blue	0.00332	0.00563	-0.00070
Bias_mu_mmle	0.00326	0.00648	-0.00019
Bias_mu_huber	0.00419	0.00637	-0.00024
Bias_sd_blue	0.35421	0.25923	0.11630
Bias_sd_mle	0.23129	0.18125	0.11316
Bias_sd_huber	-0.21336	-0.19717	-0.17708
MSE_mu_blue	0.08462	0.05787	0.00233
MSE_mu_mmle	0.08673	0.05827	0.00164

MSE_mu_huber	0.08629	0.05961	0.00167
MSE_sd_blue	0.34969	0.18012	0.01719
MSE_sd_mmle	0.26810	0.14772	0.01556
MSE_sd_huber	0.15072	0.11494	0.03352
RE_mu_mmle_vs_blue	1.02493	1.00692	0.70283
RE_sd_mmle_vs_blue	0.76668	0.82012	0.90512
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	1.01980	1.03018	0.71777
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.43100	0.63815	1.94936

Table 6: Results when data is from 0.90LTS + 0.10Laplace (0, c=3)

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	0.00133	-0.00237	-0.00044
mu_mmle	0.00206	-0.00299	-0.00071
mu_huber	0.00276	-0.00246	-0.00081
sd_blue	1.47778	1.35921	1.23211
sd_mle	1.36685	1.30304	1.21314
sd_huber	0.81393	0.82348	0.84149
Bias_mu_blue	0.00133	-0.00237	-0.00044
Bias_mu_mmle	0.00206	-0.00299	-0.00071
Bias_mu_huber	0.00276	-0.00246	-0.00081
Bias_sd_blue	0.47778	0.35921	0.23211
Bias_sd_mle	0.36685	0.30304	0.21314
Bias_sd_huber	-0.18607	-0.17652	-0.15851
MSE_mu_blue	0.09666	0.06264	0.00343
MSE_mu_mmle	0.10185	0.06371	0.00184
MSE_mu_huber	0.09772	0.06488	0.00185
MSE_sd_blue	0.58811	0.30130	0.06027
MSE_sd_mmle	0.55733	0.29346	0.04993
MSE_sd_huber	0.14921	0.11101	0.02748
RE_mu_mmle_vs_blue	1.05370	1.01714	0.53659
RE_sd_mmle_vs_blue	0.94766	0.97398	0.82844
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	1.01095	1.03583	0.54078
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.25371	0.36842	0.45595

Table 7: Results when data is from 0.90LTS + 0.10Laplace (0, c=4)

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	-0.00520	0.00286	0.00005
mu_mmle	-0.00552	0.00435	-0.00066
mu_huber	-0.00497	0.00431	-0.00075
sd_blue	1.61752	1.45567	1.35312
sd_mle	1.51925	1.42650	1.31769
sd_huber	0.83784	0.84111	0.85289
Bias_mu_blue	-0.00520	0.00286	0.00005
Bias_mu_mmle	-0.00552	0.00435	-0.00066
Bias_mu_huber	-0.00497	0.00431	-0.00075
Bias_sd_blue	0.61752	0.45567	0.35312
Bias_sd_mle	0.51925	0.42650	0.31769
Bias_sd_huber	-0.16216	-0.15889	-0.14711
MSE_mu_blue	0.11089	0.06795	0.00466
MSE_mu_mmle	0.11967	0.06951	0.00191
MSE_mu_huber	0.10952	0.06945	0.00189
MSE_sd_blue	0.93638	0.45064	0.13594

MSE_sd_mmle	0.92341	0.50865	0.10828
MSE_sd_huber	0.15996	0.11095	0.02400
RE_mu_mmle_vs_blue	1.07921	1.02306	0.40967
RE_sd_mmle_vs_blue	0.98615	1.12873	0.79653
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	0.98768	1.02213	0.40461
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.17082	0.24621	0.17654

2.1.3 Contaminated models

In models with LTS contamination (Tables 8–10), the impact of contamination was more pronounced on BLUE-type and MMLE, with substantial increases in scale bias and MSE for small samples. Huber estimators consistently downweighted the contaminating observations, demonstrating superior robustness. Across all simulations, BLUE-type was robust for small samples with LTS data but less efficient than Huber under contamination; MMLE provided efficiency in near-ideal conditions but was sensitive to outliers.

Table 8: Results when data is from 0.90LTS + 0.10 LTS (0, c=2)

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	0.00252	-0.00363	-0.00020
mu_mmle	0.00215	-0.00287	-0.00002
mu_huber	0.00270	-0.00363	-0.00001
sd_blue	1.46069	1.34702	1.22318
sd_mle	1.34726	1.28749	1.19558
sd_huber	0.80572	0.81748	0.83123
Bias_mu_blue	0.00252	-0.00363	-0.00020
Bias_mu_mmle	0.00215	-0.00287	-0.00002
Bias_mu_huber	0.00270	-0.00363	-0.00001
Bias_sd_blue	0.46069	0.34702	0.22318
Bias_sd_mle	0.34726	0.28749	0.19558
Bias_sd_huber	-0.19428	-0.18252	-0.16877
MSE_mu_blue	0.09599	0.06416	0.00324
MSE_mu_mmle	0.10077	0.06532	0.00172
MSE_mu_huber	0.09651	0.06650	0.00174
MSE_sd_blue	0.53672	0.29062	0.05632
MSE_sd_mmle	0.45735	0.26501	0.04246
MSE_sd_huber	0.15059	0.11735	0.03078
RE_mu_mmle_vs_blue	1.04981	1.01799	0.53081
RE_sd_mmle_vs_blue	0.85213	0.91187	0.75399
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	1.00538	1.03885	0.53654
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.28057	0.40379	0.54653

Table 9: Results when data is from 0.90LTS + 0.10 LTS (0, c=3)

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	0.00356	-0.00385	-0.00139
mu_mmle	0.00404	-0.00360	-0.00102
mu_huber	0.00255	-0.00367	-0.00120
sd_blue	1.63847	1.46603	1.39744
sd_mle	1.55406	1.44924	1.34309
sd_huber	0.82981	0.83611	0.84784
Bias_mu_blue	0.00356	-0.00385	-0.00139
Bias_mu_mmle	0.00404	-0.00360	-0.00102
Bias_mu_huber	0.00255	-0.00367	-0.00120

Bias_sd_blue	0.63847	0.46603	0.39744
Bias_sd_mle	0.55406	0.44924	0.34309
Bias_sd_huber	-0.17019	-0.16399	-0.15216
MSE_mu_blue	0.10888	0.06506	0.00601
MSE_mu_mmle	0.11922	0.06752	0.00200
MSE_mu_huber	0.10644	0.06679	0.00193
MSE_sd_blue	0.99418	0.47167	0.17230
MSE_sd_mmle	1.00594	0.53778	0.12574
MSE_sd_huber	0.15423	0.11004	0.02552
RE_mu_mmle_vs_blue	1.09499	1.03775	0.33242
RE_sd_mmle_vs_blue	1.01182	1.14018	0.72981
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	0.97759	1.02656	0.32165
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.15513	0.23330	0.14814

Table 10: Results when data is from 0.90LTS + 0.10 LTS (0, c=4)

Sample Size	10	15	500
mu_blue	0.00182	-0.00236	-0.00090
mu_mmle	0.00390	0.00094	-0.00025
mu_huber	-0.00017	0.00141	-0.00015
sd_blue	1.80807	1.60260	1.57754
sd_mle	1.74760	1.64030	1.49755
sd_huber	0.83768	0.85596	0.85635
Bias_mu_blue	0.00182	-0.00236	-0.00090
Bias_mu_mmle	0.00390	0.00094	-0.00025
Bias_mu_huber	-0.00017	0.00141	-0.00015
Bias_sd_blue	0.80807	0.60260	0.57754
Bias_sd_mle	0.76160	0.64030	0.49755
Bias_sd_huber	-0.14404	-0.14365	-0.14365
MSE_mu_blue	0.11930	0.07375	0.00920
MSE_mu_mmle	0.13616	0.07752	0.00206
MSE_mu_huber	0.11107	0.07347	0.00193
MSE_sd_blue	1.62653	0.77383	0.36111
MSE_sd_mmle	1.84873	1.02057	0.26279
MSE_sd_huber	0.15979	0.11738	0.02305
RE_mu_mmle_vs_blue	1.13538	1.06124	0.22433
RE_sd_mmle_vs_blue	1.13661	1.31884	0.72775
RE_mu_huber_vs_blue	0.92617	0.99631	0.20925
RE_sd_huber_vs_blue	0.09824	0.15168	0.06384

2.1.4 Weights from different methods

In small samples, the BLUE-type estimator assigned lower weights to extreme values, reducing their influence on the estimates. For larger samples, both MMLE and Huber estimators effectively downweighted outliers, maintaining robustness against extreme observations. Overall, BLUE-type is more conservative with extremes in small datasets, while MMLE and Huber perform robustly with larger data.

Figure 1: Weight functions of BLUE-type, MML, and Huber estimators across sample sizes.

3. Application

Temperature extremes have a profound impact on human health, making them a central concern in public health research and policy. Exposure to extreme heat can cause heat stroke, heat exhaustion, dehydration, and muscle cramps, while extreme cold can lead to hypothermia, frostbite, and exacerbate pre-existing cardiovascular and respiratory conditions. Vulnerable populations, including the elderly, children, and individuals with chronic illnesses, are particularly susceptible to these adverse health outcomes. Continuous monitoring and characterization of temperature extremes are therefore essential to guide early interventions, optimize healthcare resource allocation, and inform policy decisions aimed at protecting communities during extreme weather events.

According to the U.S. Drought Monitor Map (August 23, 2023), Louisiana experienced extreme drought conditions, ranking among the most affected states in the nation. To assess environmental stress during this period, we analyzed daily maximum temperature values recorded at the New Orleans International Airport (MSY) from August 1 to August 31, 2023. The dataset, obtained from the Southern Climate Impacts Planning Program (SCIPP) Louisiana Climate Data Portal, provides monthly temperature observations that reflect regional climatic patterns. In our study, we focused on modeling the location parameter (μ) of the temperature distribution using a Long-Tailed Symmetric (LTS) framework, which accounts for the heavy-tailed nature commonly observed in environmental and climate data. Temperature data, particularly from summer months and drought periods, often deviates from the Gaussian assumption due to the presence of extreme values. Consistent with this pattern, the dataset used in our analysis exhibited non-normality, as shown in the histogram and Q-Q plot (Figure 2). The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test confirmed a significant deviation from normality ($D = 0.194$, $p < 0.01$).

Figure 2: Normality Testing of daily maximum temperature data. (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test = 0.194, p-value < 0.010).

Table 11 presents the location estimates and their standard errors for $p = 5$ and $n = 31$. All three methods produced similar mean estimates (MMLE: 98.45, BLUE-type: 98.47, Huber: 98.30). The BLUE-type estimator had slightly higher precision than Huber, while MMLE showed the smallest standard error (0.606), indicating marginally greater efficiency.

Table 11: Location estimates and their corresponding standard errors

	MMLE	Blue-type	Huber
mean	98.45	98.47	98.30
standard error	0.606	0.625	0.662

*Here, $p=5$ & $n=31$

4. Discussion

This study demonstrates the importance of using robust estimation methods when modeling environmental data characterized by heavy-tailed distributions, such as temperature extremes during drought conditions. Traditional estimators often rely on the assumption of normally distributed errors, an assumption frequently violated in real-world climate data. During August 2023, Louisiana experienced one of the most severe droughts in the United States, resulting in extremely high daily maximum temperatures and greater variability in the upper tail of the distribution. These features make conventional methods less reliable and motivate the use of robust approaches like the Long-Tailed Symmetric (LTS) framework.

Our comparison of estimators revealed that the Modified Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MMLE) provided the most efficient and stable estimates, reflected by its lowest variance among all methods considered. This result is consistent with theoretical expectations, as the MMLE method maximizes the likelihood under the LTS model and optimally adjusts for tail behavior. The BLUE-type estimator also performed well, maintaining robustness and unbiasedness in small samples, while the Huber estimator showed higher variability due to its greater sensitivity to tail weight adjustments.

Overall, the BLUE-type estimators demonstrated greater robustness in estimating the location parameter under the Long-Tailed Symmetric (LTS) distribution, particularly when the sample size was small. However, this robustness advantage may not necessarily extend to other distributional settings. Compared with the MMLE and Huber estimators, the BLUE estimators exhibited higher efficiency, as they assign less weight to extreme tail observations, thereby reducing the influence of outliers in small-sample scenarios.

In broader terms, applying statistically efficient and robust estimators to environmental datasets enhances the accuracy of early detection systems for temperature anomalies and supports more informed public health planning. By capturing the true underlying variability of temperature extremes, such models can contribute to developing better early-warning systems and targeted mitigation strategies for at-risk populations.

Future research directions include investigating the weighting structure of these estimators for varying shape parameters and sample sizes, extending simulations to other symmetric distributions like Laplace, and comparing results with alternative robust estimators, such as Tukey's Biweight. These analyses will help generalize the robustness and efficiency properties observed here and further strengthen the methodological foundation for modeling environmental data under non-normal conditions.

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References

- Ahmad, A., A. Sanullah and M. Hanif (2020). "Modified maximum likelihood integrated robust ratio estimator in simple random sampling." Punjab University Journal of Mathematics **51**(3).
- Arnold, B. C. and N. Balakrishnan (2012). Relations, bounds and approximations for order statistics, Springer Science & Business Media.
- Cochran, W. (1940). "The estimation of the yields of cereal experiments by sampling for the ratio of grain to total produce." The journal of agricultural science **30**(2): 262-275.
- Huber, P. J. (1984). "Finite Sample Breakdown of S and P -Estimators." The Annals of Statistics **12**(1): 119-126.
- Lloyd, E. H. (1952). "Least-squares estimation of location and scale parameters using order statistics." Biometrika **39**(1/2): 88-95.
- Murthy, M. N. (1967). "Sampling theory and methods."
- Oral, E. and C. Kadilar (2011). "Pak. J. Statist. 2011 Vol. 27 (3), 269-282 IMPROVED RATIO ESTIMATORS VIA MODIFIED MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD." Pak. J. Statist **27**(3): 269-282.
- Prasad, B. (1989). "Some improved ratio type estimators of population mean and ratio in finite population sample surveys." Communications in Statistics - Theory and Methods **18**(1): 379-392.
- Sani, Y. M. A., A.; Abbas, U. F. (2023). "Improved ratio estimators of population mean using linear combination of auxiliary variable location parameters." International Journal of Engineering Inventions **12**(10): 59-68.
- Swain, A. (2014). "On an improved ratio type estimator of finite population mean in sample surveys." Investigación Operacional **35**(1): 49-58.
- Tiku, M. and S. Kumra (1985). "SYMMETRIC DISTRIBUTIONS (STUDENT'St)." Three Sets of Tables: Expected Sizes of a Selected Subset in Paired Comparison Experiments; Tables of Admissible and Optimal Balanced Treatment Incomplete Block (BTIB) Designs for Comparing Treatments with a Control; Expected Values and Variances and Covariances of Order Statistics for a Family of Symmetric Distributions **7**: 141.
- Tiku, M. and R. Suresh (1992). "A new method of estimation for location and scale parameters." Journal of Statistical Planning and Inference **30**(2): 281-292.